

1 **The role of tillage practices in wheat straw decomposition and shaping the associated microbial communities**
2 **in *Endocalcaric* – *Epigleyic Cambisol* soil.**

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8

9 **Abstract**

10 The recalcitrant nature of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) straw, one of the most abundant agricultural residues, presents
11 challenges for efficient decomposition, limiting nutrient release and organic matter retention in soils. Understanding
12 the effects of tillage practices on wheat straw decomposition and shaping associated microbial communities is essential
13 for enhancing microbial-mediated breakdown and optimizing residue management to enhance soil health, nutrient
14 cycling, and sustainability in agricultural systems. In this study, the effect of different tillage practices on wheat straw
15 decomposition and associated bacterial and fungal community compositions during non-growing and growing seasons
16 were studied. To simulate tillage, litter bags filled with wheat straw were placed at respective soil depths for
17 conventional (22-24 cm) and reduced (8-10 cm) tillage, and on the surface for the no-tillage treatment. The subsets of
18 the litter bags were randomly retrieved after 145 days and at the end of the experiment after 290 days. Statistical
19 analysis revealed that tillage treatments significantly influenced the decomposition rate and nutrient release over time.
20 Overall, the alpha diversity of the decomposition-associated microbial community was not substantially affected by
21 different tillage treatments, while beta diversity exhibited distinct microbial community compositions in relation to
22 tillage practices. The results of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of wheat straw decomposition-
23 associated bacterial and fungal communities' response to different tillage treatments, with observations made at two
24 distinct sampling times (non-growing and growing seasons) under certain edaphic and climatic conditions.

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28 **Keywords:** Wheat straw, tillage, decomposition, litter microbial communities

29 **Introduction**

30 Crop residue is widely acknowledged as one of the primary and most important sources of organic matter in soil,
31 particularly in the context of modern agriculture (Bisen and Rahangdale 2017; Turmel et al. 2015). Among various
32 crop residue management practices, incorporation and retention have been widely recognized as an effective,
33 sustainable and environmentally friendly strategy for enhancing soil organic carbon and nutrient recycling (Bisen and
34 Rahangdale 2017; Haas et al. 2022; Yadvinder-Singh et al. 2005). Nevertheless, the efficacy of these strategies may
35 vary depending on the distinct tillage practices implemented and the residue type (Pu et al., 2019).

36 In Lithuania, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a major cereal crop, accounting for about 85% of the main
37 cereal crop residue production (Shamshitov et al. 2024). Due to the recalcitrant nature of cereal crop residues, typically
38 associated with a high carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C/N) and the presence of complex lignocellulosic structures results in
39 a slower decomposition rate (Habets et al. 2013). Hence, selecting appropriate tillage practices for cereal crop residue
40 management, which can accelerate the decomposition rate, while simultaneously enhancing nutrient recycling and the
41 associated microbial community is crucial. These strategies might directly or indirectly impact on the soil
42 environment, subsequently influencing the diversity, abundance, and activity of microorganisms involved in residue
43 decomposition (Mathew et al. 2012; Smith et al. 2016; Shamshitov et al. 2022).

44 Conventional tillage (CT), encompassing methods like ploughing and turning the soil, significantly disrupts
45 the upper soil horizon, creating a homogeneous soil layer with uniform physical characteristics and nutrient
46 distribution (Kaurin et al. 2015; Sun et al. 2018). Furthermore, the physical incorporation of crop residues promoted
47 by CT enhances contact between soil microorganisms and residues, accelerating decomposition and promoting the
48 proliferation of aerobic microorganisms. This results in improved soil aeration, increased porosity, and enhanced
49 oxygen diffusion, which initially favors the breakdown of organic matter (Doyeni et al. 2024; Erickson 2015; Zhao et
50 al. 2017). However, these benefits are tempered by long-term effects, as the repeated disturbance from tillage can lead
51 to a decrease in soil organic matter, alter the composition of soil microbial communities including bacteria and fungi,
52 and reduce biodiversity and microbial biomass (Legrand et al. 2018; Schmidt et al. 2018; Simmons and Coleman

53 2008). In contrast, reduced tillage (RT) and no-tillage (NT) practices facilitate conservation agriculture by minimizing
54 soil disturbance, maintaining soil structure, and preserving soil organic matter, they also provide a more stable habitat
55 for a diverse range of microorganisms (FAO 2016; Mathew et al. 2012; Wang et al. 2017c). The Intermediate
56 Disturbance Hypothesis posits that the highest value of diversity is achieved in ecosystems that experience moderate
57 levels of disturbance (Connell 1978; Grime 1973). Thus, it is presumed that in the context of agriculture by applying
58 the principles of the Intermediate Disturbance Hypothesis, RT might create conditions that promote higher biodiversity
59 of microorganisms, particularly those associated with crop residue decomposition.

60 Numerous studies have investigated the influence of agricultural practices on soil microbial community
61 composition across various soil types and climatic conditions (Carmona et al. 2020; Cloutier et al. 2023; Degruene et
62 al. 2016; Jiménez-Bueno et al. 2016; Kerdraon et al. 2019; Navarro-Noya et al. 2022; Nivelle et al. 2016; Smith et al.
63 2016; Sun et al. 2018; Tyler 2019). Regardless of the molecular or metabolic approaches employed, these studies
64 consistently demonstrate that agricultural management practices, by altering soil physical and chemical properties,
65 influence the composition, dynamics, and functional diversity of soil microbial communities. For instance,
66 conservation tillage practices promote more stable fungal communities compared to conventional tillage (Mathew et
67 al. 2012; Orru et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2017b), while straw returning increased the diversity of both soil bacterial and
68 fungal communities (Guan et al. 2023; Su et al. 2020; Zhang et al. 2023).

69 The majority of these studies focused on shifts in community composition and the dynamics of the relative
70 abundance of various taxonomic groups in bulk and rhizosphere soils. However, little is known about how tillage
71 practices affect microbiota associated with crop residue decomposition, which mediates this process. Additionally, the
72 mechanisms driving the shift from copiotrophic to oligotrophic microorganisms during residue decomposition, and
73 how tillage practices affect this pattern, are not well understood. Addressing these knowledge gaps is essential for
74 improving our understanding of microbial-mediated nutrient release from lignocellulosic materials for optimizing
75 wheat residue management and tillage practices to enhance soil fertility and nutrient cycling. Therefore, this study
76 aimed to evaluate the effect of different tillage practices in a cereal-based cropping system on the decomposition of
77 wheat straw and associated bacterial and fungal community compositions. Parameters of wheat straw decomposition,
78 combined with high-throughput sequencing of bacterial 16S rRNA genes and fungal ITS2 regions, were used to
79 analyze the successional patterns of these communities during both the non-growing and growing seasons.

80 **Material and methods**

81 **Experimental site and conditions**

82 The litter bag experiment was part of a long-term tillage experiment that is being conducted at the Institute of
83 Agriculture of Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry in 2022-2023. The long-term experiment was
84 established in Akademija, Central Lithuania (55°23'50"N, 23°51'40"E) in 2003. According to the World Reference
85 Base for Soil Resources (IUSS Working Group WRB 2022), the soil is classified as an *Endocalcari – Epihypogleyic*
86 *Cambisol*, of a loam texture. Tillage treatments selected for the litter bag experiment include conventional tillage (CT)
87 (ploughing, 22–24 cm), reduced tillage (RT) (harrowing, 8–10 cm) and no-tillage (NT) (direct drilling). The field
88 experiment is arranged as a randomized complete block design in four replications. Cereal cropping sequences
89 consisting of five-member crop rotations (winter wheat – winter oil seed rape - spring wheat - spring barley - field
90 pea) has a history of more than three complete rotation cycles. In 2021/2022, winter oilseed rape was cultivated,
91 followed by spring wheat in 2023. Spring wheat 'Akvilon' at seed rate of 200 kg ha⁻¹ was drilled on April 24, 2023.
92 Alongside sowing, mineral NPK fertilizers were applied at the following dose rates: nitrogen at 10 kg active ingredient
93 (a.i.) ha⁻¹, phosphorus at 43 kg a.i. ha⁻¹, and potassium at 90 kg a.i. ha⁻¹. To manage broadleaved weed populations, a
94 tank mixture of herbicides was applied on May 29, comprising 500 g ha⁻¹ MCPA (2-methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic
95 acid), 15 g ha⁻¹ amidosulfuron, and 10 g ha⁻¹ tribenuron-methyl. For the control of monocotyledonous weed species,
96 pinoxaden was applied at a rate of 35 g ha⁻¹ on June 6. To support crop growth, additional nitrogen fertilization was
97 provided at the tillering to stem elongation stages, with 120 kg a.i. ha⁻¹ of nitrogen supplied in the form of ammonium
98 nitrate.

99 **Litter bags for residue decomposition measurements**

100 Fresh wheat straw was collected (August 2022), air-dried to standardize moisture content and minimize variability in
101 initial microbial load, and cut into 1-2 cm lengths to ensure consistency in sampling and analysis, and to mimic the
102 natural breakdown pattern following field tillage. Further, twenty grams of straw were placed into nylon bags with
103 dimensions of 15 cm × 18 cm and a mesh size of 0.1 mm. A total of 120 litter bags containing wheat residue were
104 placed in the field experiment on 4 November 2022, one week after the tillage treatments were performed. This number
105 of litter bags was selected to ensure that sufficient residue remained after each sampling time for all planned analyses.
106 To simulate the tillage treatment, the litter bags were buried at a depth of approximately 8-10 cm in RT treatment and

107 22-24 cm in CT treatment, while in NT treatment they were placed on the surface. From each tillage treatment block
108 (4 blocks), five litter bags were randomly retrieved after 145 days (28 March 2023), and 290 days (20 August 2023)
109 of decomposition. The first 145 days coincided with a non-growing season, and the following 145 days with a growing
110 season, respectively. Upon retrieval, one litter bag from each block was immediately placed in an insulated box with
111 ice, transported to the laboratory, and stored at -81°C for subsequent DNA extraction. The remaining four litter bags
112 from each block were cleaned gently using a brush to remove adherent soil, then air-dried at 55 °C and weighed to
113 determine the dry weight of remaining wheat residues, subsequently processed for chemical analysis. To account for
114 any error due to soil in the litter bags, the contents of each bag were ignited for four hours at 600 °C. Ash content was
115 measured both before and after decomposition. The decomposed weight of wheat straw was adjusted according to the
116 initial and final weight of the ashes. The remaining straw mass X_t was calculated as the difference between initial
117 straw mass X_0 and straw mass loss at time t . The decomposition rate constant (k) was calculated using the exponential
118 decay model by Olson (1963) using the following equation:

$$119 \quad k = -\ln \left(\frac{X_t}{X_0} \right) / t,$$

120 **Chemical analysis of decomposed wheat residue**

121 Wheat straw quality was initially determined in undecomposed (the initial) straw and again at the two sampling dates.
122 Total carbon (C) content determined by sulfochromic oxidation method, using spectrophotometry using glucose as a
123 standard, following ISO 14235:1998 for soil and its adapted version for straw (ISO 14235:1998 1998). Total nitrogen
124 (N) content was determined according to the Kjeldahl method using a final photometric determination (UV/Vis Cary
125 50 Conc) (ISO 11261:1995 1995). Acid detergent lignin (ADL) was determined after Acid detergent fiber (ADF)
126 analysis in the ANKOM fiber analyzer using cell wall detergent fractionation method according to ANKOM
127 Technology (Ankom Technology 2017; Ankom Technology 2020). The nutrient release dynamics during wheat straw
128 decomposition under different tillage treatments were calculated as follows:

$$129 \quad \text{Nutrient remaining (\%)} = \left(\frac{W_t}{W_0} \right) \times \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} \right) \times 100,$$

130 where W_t is the remaining mass at time t , W_0 is the initial weight of the wheat straw, C_t is the concentration of nutrients
131 in decomposing litter at the time of sampling and C_0 is the initial concentration of nutrients. Positive and negative
132 results indicate net mineralization and accumulation, respectively.

133 The Jarque-Bera test was used to ensure the data normality. A repeated-measures analysis of variance
134 (ANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of tillage treatment and sampling time, and their interaction on wheat
135 straw mass loss and nutrient release dynamics. Tillage treatment was considered the "between-subject" component,
136 whereas time was considered the "within-subject" variable. Post hoc pairwise comparisons with Benjamini-Hochberg
137 correction were performed to explore the significant interaction effect. The correlation matrix heatmap was prepared
138 to show the values of the Pearson correlation coefficient. All the analysis and visualizations, including plots and
139 heatmaps, were conducted using "R" version 4.3.2 (R Core Team 2023).

140 **DNA extraction, amplicon preparation, and sequencing**

141 Prior to DNA extraction, 2 g of each wheat residue sample was placed into stainless steel containers along with a 1
142 cm diameter steel ball. The containers were frozen in liquid nitrogen for 5 minutes. After removing the nitrogen, the
143 setup was fixed in the special holders of the Retsch MM 301 mill (Retsch, Haan, Germany) and homogenized for 4
144 minutes at 25 Hz. Then, the samples were stored in sterile 15 ml tubes at -20 °C until the DNA extraction. Total DNA
145 was extracted using the FastDNA spin kit for soil (MP Biomedicals, California, United States). Briefly, about 0.3 g of
146 wheat straw sample was weighed and homogenized by bead beating in the FastPrep®-24 instrument (MP Biomedical)
147 at 6 m/s for 40 seconds. The subsequent steps were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions. The DNA
148 purity and quantity were measured using an ND-1000 Spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, Wilmington,
149 United States). The DNA concentration was normalized (10 ng/mL), the V3-V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene was
150 amplified with Pro341F and Pro805R primers (Takahashi et al. 2014) and the ITS2 region was amplified with
151 ITS3_KYO2 (Toju et al. 2012) and ITS4r (White et al. 1990), respectively. Amplicons preparation and sequencing
152 were performed at BMR genomics (Padova, Italy) by MiSeq Illumina (Illumina, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA) with a
153 300PE strategy.

154 **Bioinformatic and statistical elaborations**

155 Primer sequences were removed using Cutadapt (Martin 2011). Read quality was evaluated and reads (R1 and R2)
156 were then trimmed and filtered with the following parameters: truncLen = c (16S 280,170; ITS2 270,175), maxN = 0,
157 maxEE = c (2,2), and truncQ = 2. Reads were merged with an overlap of at least 12 bases, ensuring identical sequences
158 in the overlap region. Chimeras were removed, and amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) for bacteria were classified
159 against the Silva database v139 (Yilmaz et al. 2014), while fungi were classified against the UNITE database

160 (Abarenkov et al. 2023). The classification was performed using the assign Taxonomy function in the DADA2 package
161 version 1.18.0. (Callahan et al. 2016) in “R” version 4.3.2 (R Core Team 2023). ASVs matching with chloroplast and
162 mitochondria sequences were removed from the ASV table. The α -diversity measures (number of observed ASVs,
163 Chao1 value, Pielou’s evenness and Shannon indexes) were calculated using the vegan package, version 2.5–7
164 (Oksanen et al. 2020). Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) and permutational multivariate analysis of
165 variance (PERMANOVA) based on Hellinger-transformed ASV abundance data were performed using the metaMDS
166 and the adonis2 functions, respectively. Both the NMDS and the PERMANOVA were performed with the Bray–Curtis
167 dissimilarity index. Shapiro–Wilk and Levene tests were performed to check normality and homogeneity of variance,
168 respectively. Depending on the results, ANOVA or Kruskal–Wallis group test with false discovery rate (“fdr”) p-value
169 adjustment followed by Tukey’s HSD or Dunn’s post hoc tests were used. To elucidate the relationships among the
170 samples, heat maps were constructed representing the relative abundance at the phyla and genera levels. All statistical
171 tests were conducted in “R” version 4.3.2 (R Core Team 2023).

172 **Accession numbers**

173 Sequences have been deposited in the National Center for Biotechnology Information's (NCBI) GenBank Sequence
174 Read Archive (SRA) under the PRJNA1175890.

175 **Results**

176 **Wheat straw decomposition**

177 After 145 days (March 28) of the litter bag experiment, wheat straw had lost ~16.01% ($\pm 1.23\%$), ~15.67% ($\pm 1.43\%$),
178 and ~12.61% ($\pm 0.74\%$) of its initial mass under CT, RT, and NT treatments, respectively (Fig. 1A). Tillage treatment
179 type significantly influenced the decomposition of wheat straw showing that decomposition progresses significantly
180 over the observed periods ($F_{\text{tillage}} = 77.47$; $F_{\text{time}} = 1564.92$, $p < 0.001$). The significant interaction effect between
181 tillage treatment and sampling time ($F = 117.63$, $p < 0.001$) confirms that the impact of tillage treatment on wheat
182 straw decomposition is time-dependent, with variations in decomposition rates becoming more pronounced over time.
183 The lowest remaining mass after 290 days was observed under CT 10123.08 mg (± 53.13 mg), which explains the
184 highest k value indicating fast decomposition among tillage treatments (Fig. 1B). The calculation of time (days) needed

185 to reach half-life and 95% loss of wheat straw initial mass loss in the litter bag confirms that scenario cold and non-
 186 growing period requires more time for the decomposition (Fig. 1C and D).

187 The results of the chemical analysis of wheat straw revealed varied changes in respective components. At
 188 145 days C release already showed substantial differences across the treatments (Fig. 1E). For instance, the pairwise
 189 comparisons elucidated a notable difference between CT vs NT (estimate = -10.39, $p = 0.0012$), and NT vs RT
 190 (estimate = 7.01, $p = 0.0274$) at this sampling time. The highest C release after 290 days from wheat straw was
 191 observed under RT ~ 64.47% ($\pm 1.46\%$), followed by CT ~ 59.37% ($\pm 1.40\%$) and NT ~ 23.65% ($\pm 1.70\%$), respectively.
 192 Figure 1D shows that the release of N was noted only at the first sampling point under NT and RT treatments, relative
 193 to the initial N content in the wheat straw. In contrast, CT treatment showed a net increase in N content from the
 194 beginning. Furthermore, by 290 days, N had significantly accumulated in all tillage treatments. This observation is
 195 supported by the highly significant effect of time on N changes in wheat straw during the decomposition process ($F =$
 196 459.736, $p < 0.001$).

197

198 Figure 1. Decomposition rate and chemical parameters of wheat straw. A remaining mass, B decomposition rate
 199 constant (k), C half-life ($t_{0.50}$) of wheat straw, D time required for 95% ($t_{0.95}$) decomposition of wheat straw, E-I
 200 chemical parameters and nutrient changes after 145 and 290 days.

201 Comparatively different degradation patterns were observed for lignin while comparing it with other wheat
 202 straw components (Fig. 1G). The findings indicated a significant main effect of tillage treatment on lignin content (F
 203 = 55.85, $p < 0.001$), similarly, the effect of time was also significant ($F = 49.62$, $p < 0.001$). However, the interaction
 204 between tillage treatment and time was not statistically significant ($F = 2.52$, $p = 0.135$), corresponding that the impact
 205 of tillage treatment on lignin content does not alter substantially over time. The initial wheat straw C/N ratio was 110.6
 206 whereas after 290 days it ranged from 35.6 to 63.5 depending on the tillage treatment. The results of statistical analysis
 207 revealed a significant interaction between-subject and within-subject factors on the C/N ratio, as well as separately
 208 each factor ($F_{\text{interaction}} = 21.31$; $F_{\text{tillage}} = 51.02$; $F_{\text{time}} = 352.07$, $p < 0.001$). The lignin/N ratio significantly decreased
 209 over time in decomposing wheat straw under all tillage treatments.

211 Figure 2. Heat map of Pearson's correlation coefficient of wheat straw decomposition and chemical parameters.
212 Remaining mass (RM), decomposition rate constant (k), half-life time of decomposition ($t_{0.50}$), the time required for
213 95% decomposition ($t_{0.95}$), remaining carbon (C), remaining nitrogen (N), remaining lignin (Lignin), C/N, and
214 Lignin/N ratios. The correlation coefficients range from -1 to 1, where values closer to 1 indicate a strong positive
215 correlation, values closer to -1 indicate a strong negative correlation, and values around 0 indicate no linear correlation.
216 The color gradient from red to blue in the heatmap represents the correlation coefficient values, with red indicating
217 positive correlations and blue indicating negative correlations.

218 The correlation matrix heatmap displays the Pearson correlation coefficient values, which are the linear
219 relationships between various decomposition-related variables (Fig. 2). The remaining straw mass strongly correlated
220 with the remaining C, half-life time ($t_{0.50}$), time required for 95% decomposition ($t_{0.95}$), C/N ratio and lignin, whereas
221 the values of the Pearson correlation coefficient marginally declined in this sequence, respectively (ranging from 0.97
222 to 0.76). Furthermore, the strong negative correlation between remaining mass and decomposition rate constant as
223 well as remaining N content (-0.94 and -0.88, respectively), suggests that high k value and remaining N content are
224 associated with lower remaining mass. Hence, the k value strongly correlated only with the remaining N content (0.72).
225 The remaining N content showed a strong negative correlation with the remaining C content (-0.81).

226 **Differences in bacterial communities associated with wheat straw decomposition**

227 A total of 2,653,560 sequences of the V3-V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene were obtained (ranging from 50,739 for
228 sample B1II_S1 to 131,643 for sample B3II_S1) with an average of 94,770 *per* sample. All libraries showed good
229 sequencing coverage (Fig. S1), and a total of 3,178 amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) were identified, ranging from
230 902 to 1,781 (Fig. S1 and 3A). The alpha-diversity was measured as Observed ASVs, Shannon diversity and Pielou's
231 evenness dividing the samples respect to the tillage treatment and sampling time, the wheat straws microbiota at the
232 beginning of the experiments was characterized as well (Fig. 3A-C). The bacterial community of the wheat straws at
233 the beginning of the experiment was characterized by a low number of observed ASVs (948 ± 25) and a low value of
234 the diversity indices. After 145 days there was recorded an increase of the observed ASVs in all the different treatments
235 possibly indicating colonization of the wheat straws within the litter bags by the soil bacteria, however, no significant
236 differences were observed among the treatments (Fig. 3A and Table S1). Similarly, an increase of the Shannon and
237 Pielou's indices was observed but with no differences among treatments (Fig. 3B and C). At the end of the experiment

238 (after 290 d) the number of observed ASVs was similar for the samples treated by direct drilling (NT) while samples
239 subjected to CT or RT showed a reduction of the observed ASVs, but this was statistically significant only for the RT
240 treatment (Fig. 3A). No significant differences were observed after 290 days for Shannon and Pielou's indices (Fig.
241 3B and C).

242 NMDS analysis based on Bray-Curtis' dissimilarity index showed that the bacterial community composition
243 after 145 days was different respect to the initial community but there were no clear differences respect to the different
244 treatments, in contrast after 290 days there was a separation between all the treatments with samples treated with CT
245 or RT separated along the x-axis and clustering in two distinct groups but close each other while the samples from the
246 NT group clustered apart (Fig. 3D). These differences were confirmed by PERMANOVA analysis ($p < 0.001$ and
247 Table S2). The bacterial community composition was initially formed by 12 different phyla with the majority of reads
248 ($99.3 \pm 0.6\%$) falling into four phyla (*Proteobacteria*, *Actinobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes* and *Firmicutes* which accounted
249 for 53.7%, 27.4%, 13.5% and 4.7% respectively; Fig. 3E).

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251 Figure 3. Characterization of wheat straw decomposition-associated bacterial community. A-C alpha diversity. D

252 nMDS plot based on the Bray–Curtis index. E relative abundance of bacterial phyla.

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After 145 days the bacterial communities associated with the wheat straws treated by CT, RT and NT were significantly different respect to the initial communities but not from each other (Table S1 and Fig. 3D). Two phyla (accounting for less than 0.005%) were observed in one treatment only at 145 days: *Latescibacteria* (in RT) and *Spirochaetes* (in CT). Interestingly, the phylum *Parcubacteria* (< 0.04%) was present only at 145 days, further being absent at 290 days across all treatments. Another poorly abundant phylum (< 0.01%) *Abditibacteriota* that was present across all treatments at 290 days was observed exclusively in NT treatment. The bacterial communities were mainly

259 composed of *Proteobacteria* (ranging from 44.3% for NT to 51.1% for CT) however in all the bacterial communities
260 was observed a strong reduction of *Actinobacteria* (from 6.75% for NT to 9.8% for RT) and an increase of
261 *Bacteroidetes* (from 28% in CT to 34.9% in NT) (Fig. 3E; Fig. 4A). Other differences were related to presence/absence
262 of some phyla poorly represented (< 0.01%) as Cyanobacteria that were absent in CT, the *Deinococcus-Thermus* and
263 *Euryarchaeota* groups that were not present in NT and the RT groups respectively (Table S2).

264 At the genus level, a total of 77 genera were detected in the 16S rRNA analysis. The top 30 genera were
265 selected based on the relative abundance data of each sample, considering the species annotation and relative
266 abundance information (Fig. 4B). The initial wheat straw samples (BC1-4) consistently exhibited a dominant
267 proportion of the genus *Sphingomonas* ($17.78\% \pm 0.39\%$), which diminished further after 145 days across all tillage
268 treatments (CT $6.86\% \pm 1.52\%$, RT $5.55\% \pm 0.14\%$), and NT ($5.39\% \pm 0.92\%$). This trend continued at 290 days
269 under CT and RT (CT $4.6\% \pm 1.47\%$, RT $4.05\% \pm 0.6\%$), but significantly increased in NT ($13.33\% \pm 1.64\%$).
270 Conversely, the genus *Flavobacterium*, initially constituting slightly over 1% of the bacterial population in the initial
271 wheat straw, showed a notable increase during decomposition after 145 days. This increase was consistent across all
272 treatments, with relative abundances ranging from $13.04\% \pm 0.84\%$ in RT treatment to $15.30\% \pm 2.6\%$ in NT
273 treatment. Subsequently, however, there was a substantial decline after 290 days across all tillage treatments. A similar
274 trend was observed for the genus *Pedobacter*. The heatmap (Fig. 4B) also shows that most of the samples belonging
275 to the same tillage treatment didn't consistently group in a cluster analysis, except for the initial wheat straw, NT and
276 CT both at 290 days. Moreover, the clustering reflected the change in relative abundance of genera related to sampling
277 time.

279 Figure 4. Heat map representing the percentages of 16S rRNA gene sequences in each sample belonging to identified
280 phyla (A) and the top 30 genera (B). The intensity of the blue color indicates relative abundance. The dendrogram was
281 constructed using Pearson distance. In sample names B: bacteria; Arabic numbers (1, 3, 5): tillage treatments (1 – CT,
282 3 – RT, 5 – NT); Roman numerals (I, II, III, IV): blocks; C: initial wheat straw; _S1: sampling at 145 days; _S2:
283 sampling at 290 days.

284 **Differences in fungal communities associated with wheat straw decomposition**

285 Fungal communities were characterized by sequencing the ITS2 region, obtaining a total of 3,357,854 with an average
286 of 119,923 (ranging from 37,122 for sample F1IV_S1 to 178,645 for sample F3I_S1). Rarefaction curves showed a
287 full sequencing coverage for all libraries (Fig. S2). Analysis with DADA2 identified a total of 1458 ASVs (from 69
288 for sample F1IV_S1 to 296 for sample F5IV_S2) (Fig. S2 and 3A). The alpha diversity was measured using the same
289 indices used for bacteria (Observed ASVs, Shannon and Pielou's; Fig. 5A-C). In contrast, with the data for bacterial
290 communities the number of observed ASVs was quite similar between the fungal community of the wheat straws at
291 the beginning of the experiment and the fungal communities of the litter bags at 145 and 290 days, the only difference
292 was observed for the litter bags with NT treatments after 290 days that showed a higher number of observed ASVs
293 respect to the initial samples. A marked difference in the number of ASVs between 145 and 290 days was observed
294 for both CT and NT treatments, while in the RT the number of ASVs was stable (Fig. 5A and Table S3).

295 In contrast to both Shannon and Pielou's indices, no differences were observed (Fig. 5B and C). NMDS
296 analysis based on Bray-Curtis' dissimilarity index on fungal communities showed a distribution similar to what was
297 previously observed for bacteria (Fig. 3D and 4D). After 145 days the fungal communities showed no differences
298 among the three different treatments while at 290 days there was a clear separation between the three groups with the
299 NT group clustering further apart from the other two groups (PERMANOVA, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 5D and Table S4). At
300 the beginning of the trial, the fungal community composition was mainly formed by the *Ascomycota* ($85.6 \pm 0.8\%$)
301 and *Basidiomycota* ($13.8 \pm 0.8\%$) phyla accounting for the $99.44 \pm 0.07\%$ of the total number of reads with
302 *Mucoromycota*, *Mortierellomycota* and *Chytridiomycota* relative abundance below 0.1% (Fig. 5E). After 145 days the
303 *Ascomycota* relative abundance was still high in CT and RT groups (78% and 82% respectively) while in the NT there
304 was a high variability between samples ($62 \pm 16\%$) counterbalanced by an increase of the *Basidiomycota* group relative

305 abundance ($35 \pm 18\%$) (Fig. 5E). Together these two phyla accounted for the majority of the fungal communities: 97.5
 306 $\pm 0.9\%$ in CT and NT while only for $90.9 \pm 2.9\%$ in RT (Fig. 5E).

307
 308 Figure 5. Characterization of wheat straw decomposition-associated fungal community. A-C alpha diversity. D nMDS
 309 plot based on the Bray-Curtis index. E relative abundance of fungal phyla.

310 In all three groups was also observed the presence of an additional phylum (*Rozellomycota*) whose presence
 311 was variable among groups (from $0.27 \pm 0.09\%$ in the CT group to $4.57 \pm 2.44\%$ in the RT). At 290 days the number
 312 of *Ascomycota* was slightly reduced in all three groups, from $31.05 \pm 9.58\%$ in RT to $54.00 \pm 3.66\%$ in CT, although
 313 different samples within the same group exhibited a high variability (Fig. 5E). The *Ascomycota* relative abundance

314 reduction was countered by an increase of the *Basidiomycota* relative abundance (from $44.21 \pm 3.62\%$ in the NT group
315 to $65.45 \pm 9.86\%$ in the RT group with these two phyla still dominating the fungal communities with more than the
316 94% of the total reads in all the three groups (Fig. 5E). At 290 days the presence of the other phyla was below 1%
317 with the only exception of the *Chytridiomycota* phylum in the NT group ($1.49 \pm 0.45\%$); additionally, in only two
318 samples (from CT and RT groups) the presence of *Basidiobolomycota* was observed (Fig. 5E).

319 A heatmap (Fig. 6A) illustrates the relative abundance of the top 5 most prevalent phyla and unclassified,
320 collectively accounting for an average of $98.6\% \pm 0.07\%$ of the total sequences per sample. Notably, Pearson distance
321 measurements at the phylum level did not consistently cluster the samples into groups based on tillage treatment or
322 sampling time during the decomposition of wheat straw, except for the initial wheat straw sample. At the genus level,
323 a total of 252 genera including unclassified were observed. The relative abundance of the top 30 fungal genera
324 displayed in the heatmap Fig. 6B. The clusters illustrated by the dendrogram, similar to those at the phylum level (Fig.
325 6A), did not consistently correspond to tillage treatment or sampling time at the genus level.

326 *Phaeosphaeria* was one of the most dominant genera after 145 days across all tillage treatments, with
327 significantly higher relative abundance in CT ($38.90\% \pm 5.64\%$) compared to RT ($20.63\% \pm 6.61\%$) and NT (19.50%
328 $\pm 3.29\%$). However, by 290 days, a substantial reduction of *Phaeosphaeria* was observed in all fungal communities,
329 particularly in CT ($0.5\% \pm 0.12\%$). *Alternaria*, the most dominant genus in the initial wheat straw fungal community,
330 accounting for $33.67\% \pm 0.69\%$ of all sequences, remained dominant in RT ($27.92\% \pm 7.17\%$) and prevalent in NT
331 ($11.77\% \pm 8.64\%$) after 145 days. Nonetheless, by 290 days the relative abundance of *Alternaria* significantly declined
332 in CT ($0.41\% \pm 0.03\%$) and RT (0.08 ± 0.03), but was still present in NT ($8.53\% \pm 3.94$) fungal communities. The
333 genus *Sistotrema* was exclusively dominant only in the NT treatment both after 145 and 290 days, though not
334 consistently in all samples. Genera such as *Apodus*, *Tubaria*, *Coprinopsis*, *Athelia*, and *Calycellina*, which were absent
335 in the initial wheat straw fungal community, became prevalent after 145 and 290 days, with their presence often
336 exclusive to specific tillage treatments.

338 Figure 6. Heat map representing the percentages of ITS region sequences in each sample belonging to identified phyla
 339 (A), and top 30 genera (B). The intensity of the blue color represents relative abundance. The dendrogram was
 340 constructed using Pearson distance. In sample names F: fungi; Arabic numbers (1, 3, 5): tillage treatments (1 – CT, 3
 341 – RT, 5 – NT); Roman numerals (I, II, III, IV): blocks; C: initial wheat straw; _S1: sampling at 145 days; _S2: sampling
 342 at 290 days.

343 **Correlation between microbial taxa and wheat straw decomposition**

344 Spearman's rank correlation analysis was performed to assess the relationships between wheat straw decomposition-
 345 associated bacterial and fungal communities at the genus level and straw chemical parameters (C, N, lignin, C/N ratio,
 346 and lignin/N ratio; Fig. 7 and 8).

347
 348 Figure 7. Spearman correlations between wheat straw chemical parameters and detected top 30 bacterial genera.
 349 Significance codes: * p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.001.

350 Carbon content values changes exhibited positive correlations with the relative abundance of eleven bacteria
 351 genera, including *Flavobacterium*, *Pedobacter*, *Curtobacterium*, *Pantoea*, *Massilia*, *Agrobacterium*, *Dyadobacter*,
 352 *Hymenobacter*, *Altererythrobacter*, *Cryobacterium* and *Stenotrophomonas* (Fig. 7). Nine genera *Flavobacterium*,
 353 *Pedobacter*, *Pantoea*, *Agrobacterium*, *Dyadobacter*, *Hymenobacter*, *Altererythrobacter*, *Cryobacterium* and
 354 *Stenotrophomonas*, out of eleven and, were also positively correlated with lignin content, alongside *Aureimonas*,
 355 supporting the strong positive correlation between C and lignin content (Fig. 2). Hence, *Flavobacterium*, *Pedobacter*,
 356 *Pantoea*, *Agrobacterium*, *Altererythrobacter*, *Cryobacterium* and *Stenotrophomonas* were also positively correlated
 357 with C/N, and lignin/N ratios. Additionally, *Dyadobacter* and *Hymenobacter* were exclusively positively correlated
 358 with the C/N ratio. Interestingly, *Pseudomonas*, *Devosia*, and *Luteolibacter* genera, which did not show significant
 359 positive correlations with lignin content ($p < 0.05$), exhibited significant positive correlations with lignin/N ratio. All
 360 eleven genera positively correlated with C were negatively correlated with N content in decomposing wheat straw.
 361 Conversely, six genera *Rhizobium*, *Luteibacter*, *Mycobacterium*, *Chitinophaga*, *Sphingobium*, and
 362 *Pseudoxanthomonas* were positively correlated with N content, and negatively correlated with C content.

363

364 Figure 8. Spearman correlations between wheat straw chemical parameters and detected top 30 fungal genera.
365 Significance codes: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

366 Seven of the top thirty fungal genera, including *Phaeosphaeria*, *Alternaria*, *Helgardiomycetes*, *Vishniacozyma*,
367 *Tricellula*, *Neosascochyta*, and *Microdochium*, displayed positive correlations with changes in C content in
368 decomposing wheat straw. All of these genera, except *Tricellula*, were also positively correlated with lignin content
369 dynamics. Conversely, *Apodus*, *Tubaria*, *Calycellina*, *Hoehnelomycetaceae_gen_Incertae_sedis*, and
370 *Trichosporonales_gen_Incertae_sedis* exhibited negative correlations with C and lignin content but were positively
371 correlated with N content. The C/N and lignin/N ratios showed positive correlations with *Phaeosphaeria*, *Alternaria*,
372 *Helgardiomycetes*, *Tetracladium*, *Vishniacozyma*, *Neosascochyta*, and *Microdochium*. Additionally, the genus *Peziza*,
373 which did not exhibit significant positive correlations with lignin content ($p < 0.05$), showed significant positive
374 correlations exclusively with the lignin/N ratio.

375 Discussion

376 Effects of tillage practices on wheat straw decomposition rate and the dynamics of nutrients

377 The results of our study indicate that the influence of tillage treatment on wheat straw mass loss was time-dependent,
378 the differences in decomposition rates were more noticeable as time progressed. The decomposition in litter bags
379 during the first 145 days coincided with late autumn, winter, and early spring, typically considered the non-growing
380 season in Lithuania (Toleikiene et al. 2020). Consequently, the k value after 145 days was relatively low, which was
381 attributed to reduced microbial activity as temperatures declined during this period (Jensen et al. 2022; Urakawa et al.
382 2014). After 145 days, pairwise comparisons using the Benjamini-Hochberg correction did not reveal any significant
383 differences in remaining straw mass among the tillage treatments. However, the Compact Letter Display (CLD), which
384 provides an overall summary of group differences, indicated a difference between the CT and NT treatments. The
385 following 145 days, which coincided with the spring and summer seasons characterized by high microbial activity
386 that significantly accelerated the mass loss of the straw. Notably, the highest decomposition percentage of the original
387 weight after 290 days was observed under CT, reaching 49.38% ($\pm 0.26\%$). Furthermore, the results indicate that both
388 CT and RT exhibited significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in remaining mass compared to NT after 290 days of
389 decomposition. This aligns with previous studies indicating that residues incorporated into the soil under CT, and RT

390 decompose more rapidly than those left on the soil surface due to increased contact between soil microorganisms and
391 the residues (Beyaert and Paul Voroney 2011; Shamshitov et al. 2024; Zhao et al. 2017).

392 Consistent with the trend observed for wheat straw mass loss during the decomposition, the remaining C
393 content decreased steadily over time as well, regardless of the tillage management. The differences in C release from
394 the wheat straw became evident after just 145 days of decomposition in litter bags, with over 15% of the initial C
395 content being released across all treatments. After 290 days, the dynamics of C release shifted slightly, with the highest
396 loss observed under RT followed by CT. This usually can be related to the fact that fungi play an essential role in the
397 degradation of carbon sources in plant residues in soil (Benocci et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2022a), and RT compared to
398 CT maintains more stable fungal communities with higher richness and abundance (Friberg et al. 2019; Gomez et al.
399 2015). Although the mentioned studies primarily focused on soil fungal communities, our study did not detect
400 significant differences in alpha diversity of fungal communities associated with wheat straw decomposition between
401 CT and RT treatments. However, analysis of beta diversity revealed that fungal communities in RT treatment were
402 distinct from those in CT, suggesting that tillage practices can influence the composition of fungal communities, even
403 if overall richness and abundance remain unaffected. As expected, pairwise comparisons at both time points indicated
404 that C release under CT and RT was significantly higher compared to NT. Similarly, Lynch et al (2016) reported that
405 surface-placed residue resulted in an average 18% lower C loss compared to buried residue. In addition, the Pearson
406 correlation indicated a strong positive correlation (0.97) between remaining mass and remaining C content. Thus,
407 these findings validate the results of previous studies, which demonstrate that tillage practices involving physical
408 disturbance of soil lead to an increase in mass loss and C release of decomposing crop residues. This acceleration can
409 be attributed to several interrelated factors including increased soil aeration, enhanced microbial activity, breakdown
410 of soil aggregates and priming effect (Adhikari et al. 2024; Ball 2013; Hidalgo et al. 2019; Kan et al. 2020; Kok et al.
411 2022; Pittarello et al. 2021; Yadav et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2024). It is worth noting that *Endocalcaric Epigleyic*
412 *Cambisol* soils, characterized by their high clay content, possess a large surface area, which facilitates the adsorption
413 and binding of organic matter which reduces the accessibility of organic matter to microbial decomposers, thereby
414 promoting its stabilization (Islam et al. 2022; Šarūnaitė et al. 2024; Toleikiene et al. 2020). In contrast, Mollisols,
415 which are typically well-aerated and have a lower proportion of clay, exhibit higher rates of organic matter
416 decomposition. This is due to enhanced microbial activity and the reduced physical protection of organic substrates,

417 allowing microbes easier access to organic matter (Li et al. 2021b; Xu et al. 2020). Thus, we can assume that the
418 decomposition of organic inputs in Cambisols can be comparatively slower than in Mollisols.

419 Crop residue chemical properties, including N and lignin contents as well as C/N and lignin/N ratios, are
420 often considered as the main factors that regulate the decomposition rate (Bradford et al. 2016; Rezig et al. 2014).
421 Typically, if N content in crop residue exceeds the amount needed for microbial decomposition net N mineralization
422 of N occurs. Conversely, if the N content is insufficient or the C/N ratio is greater than 20–30, the available inorganic
423 N in the soil will be immobilized (Cabrera et al. 2005). We assume that the initial N release from decomposing wheat
424 straw under RT and NT can be explained by the comparatively lower decomposition rate, which allows for gradual N
425 mineralization. In contrast, the rapid decomposition under CT, caused by high microbial activity led to N
426 immobilization. After 290 days, the N dynamics shifted towards immobilization even under RT and NT. This shift
427 was most likely due to the temperature rise in spring and further into summer, which increased microbial activity and
428 accelerated the decomposition rate. Consequently, microorganisms immobilized N from the soil, which was required
429 for the degradation of carbon-rich wheat straw (Cabrera et al. 2005; Curtin et al. 2008; Li et al. 2015; Reichel et al.
430 2018; Wang et al. 2015). Moreover, the remaining content of N had a strong correlation (0.72) with the k value, which
431 aligns with previous studies (Chatterjee and Acharya 2020; Wang et al. 2017a). In general, the decomposition rate of
432 crop residues with high C/N ratio (cereals) is slower compared to those with lower C/N ratio (legumes) (Johnson et
433 al. 2007; Poudel et al. 2023; Singh et al. 2020). The initial wheat straw C/N ratio (110.66 ± 2.02) is considered high
434 but typical for this type of crop residue (García-Ruiz et al. 2019). After 145 days, an increase in C/N ratios was
435 observed under both RT and NT, which is attributed to N release from the wheat straw in these treatments.
436 Furthermore, the observed interaction between treatment and time suggests that the impact of tillage on the C/N ratio
437 of decomposing wheat straw is time dependent. Pearson correlation revealed that the C/N ratio had a strong negative
438 correlation with remaining N content (-0.96) and k value (-0.72) indicating that higher initial C/N ratios are associated
439 with slower decomposition. This finding aligns with the concept that plant residues containing a high amount of carbon
440 break down at a slower rate since microorganisms require more N.

441 The C/N ratio alone is insufficient to adequately explain the rate at which crop residue decomposes in the
442 soil. Whereas, lignin, a complex heteropolymer is recognized as a recalcitrant component that constitutes up to 19%
443 of crop residues weight based on dry matter (Shamshitov et al. 2024). This compound exhibits significant resistance

444 to microbial degradation, and consequently changes in lignin content might also influence the decomposition rate
445 (Melillo et al. 1982; Zhang et al. 2022b). It was observed that the effect of tillage treatment on lignin content dynamics
446 was relatively consistent over time. However, pairwise comparison indicates that after 145 days, the remaining lignin
447 content in decomposing wheat straw was significantly lower under RT compared to NT ($p < 0.001$). The lowest
448 remaining lignin content after 290 days was again detected under RT, which was significantly lower than both CT and
449 NT. Despite the significant positive correlation (0.81) between remaining lignin content and remaining C content, the
450 decrease of lignin occurred at a notably slow rate. This aligns with the observation that lignin degradation commenced
451 only after the majority of easily degradable carbon pools, including cellulose and hemicellulose, were consumed
452 (Pascault et al. 2010b). Nonetheless, the dynamics in lignin content in this experiment suggest that RT was the most
453 efficient in the release of this recalcitrant compound from decomposing wheat straw.

454 **Effect of tillage on wheat straw decomposition associated microbial community**

455 As a result of differences and changes in the decomposition rate and nutrient release of wheat straw, we assumed that
456 tillage practices might be detrimental to associated microbial alpha diversity. This assumption was based on the
457 premise that varying decomposition rates and nutrient dynamics could alter microbial habitat conditions and resource
458 availability. However, it was observed that tillage had no significant effect on observed ASVs, Shannon's diversity,
459 or Pielou's evenness, which is consistent with previous studies (Ibáñez et al. 2024; Kraut-Cohen et al. 2020).
460 Nevertheless, studies utilizing amplicon sequencing reported that both higher (Cai et al. 2021; Dong et al. 2017; Li et
461 al. 2021a) and lower (Degrune et al. 2016; Tyler 2019) microbial alpha diversity can occur under conservation tillage
462 compared to conventional tillage practices. In the context of the study, it is important to note that the majority of
463 studies investigated the effect of tillage practices on soil microbial communities rather than crop residue
464 decomposition-associated microbial communities under various tillage practices. Even though overall alpha diversity
465 metrics did not differ significantly across tillage treatments, beta diversity indicated distinct microbial community
466 composition under different tillage treatments, particularly after 290 days of decomposition.

467 In our experiment, RT was considered as the middle ground between two extremes, namely NT and CT.
468 Hence, based on this balance of colonization and competition, we assumed that RT would allow most species to
469 coexist, unlike environments with low or high disturbance rates, which typically refer to lower diversity. However,
470 our results indicate that the microbial communities associated with wheat straw decomposition under RT did not

471 exhibit increased diversity values, and consequently, do not align with the Intermediate Disturbance Hypothesis
472 (Connell 1978; Grime 1973).

473 The composition of the microbial community (both bacterial and fungal) in straw displayed very gradual
474 shifts over the process of decomposition. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which have shown that
475 the breakdown of more complex compounds in wheat straw occurs at a slower rate, compared to other crop residues,
476 leading to a gradual change in the microbial population (Kerdraon et al. 2019; Pascault et al. 2010a). In general, the
477 succession in the composition of microbial communities in organic material underlines the transition from copiotrophs
478 to oligotrophs (Fierer et al. 2007). Even though there are no agreed-upon definitions for oligotrophs and copiotrophs,
479 efforts have been made to classify microorganisms into these categories based on their phylogeny (Ho et al. 2017).
480 Based on this generalization, bacterial and fungal taxa that undergo a considerable decline in their relative abundances
481 during succession are primarily composed of copiotrophs. It was recorded that some of bacterial taxa belonging to
482 *Alphaproteobacteria* (*Agrobacterium*), *Betaproteobacteria* (*Massilia*), *Gammaproteobacteria* (*Pseudomonas*),
483 *Actinobacteria* (*Curtobacterium*, *Microterricola*) were comparatively dominant the initial wheat straw, followed by a
484 gradual decline in the relative abundance during the decomposition, and partially correlates with previous studies
485 (Bastian et al. 2009; Chung et al. 2005; Fierer et al. 2012; Leff et al. 2015; Pepe-Ranney et al. 2016). Similarly, at the
486 lower taxonomic resolution, the fungal genera *Alternaria*, and *Cladosporium* exhibited a comparable pattern, aligning
487 with findings from other researchers (Chigineva et al. 2009; Di Lonardo et al. 2013). Conversely, the relative
488 abundance of oligotrophs, including some of the genera belonging to *Acidobacteria*, *Alphaproteobacteria* and
489 *Bacteroidetes*, as well as *Basidiomycota* phyla increased as wheat straw decomposition progressed. The
490 aforementioned trend reflects their ability to efficiently degrade complex polymers and corresponds to findings from
491 earlier research (Chen et al. 2016; Ho et al. 2017; Senechkin et al. 2010). Despite the general tendency of some
492 microbial taxa, responses to environments with high or low levels of nutrients are not always consistent, as observed
493 in this study. Furthermore, the results of this study indicate that the dynamics of certain microbial taxa in terms of
494 relative abundance were influenced by tillage practices. For instance, *Sphingomonas*, which was one of the dominant
495 bacterial genera in the initial wheat straw, significantly decreased across all tillage practices throughout the
496 experiment, except in the NT treatment after 290 days, where its relative abundance significantly increased. It is worth
497 noticing that the genus *Sphingomonas* is known to be able to degrade cellulose and hemicellulose and is considered
498 to be abundant in oligotrophic environments (Aylward et al. 2013; Koskinen et al. 2000). Moreover, it's important to

499 state that Ho et al. (2017) mention that some taxa might exhibit both copiotrophic and oligotrophic features,
500 suggesting that considering microbial community responses at finer resolutions may be more adequate.

501 CT practices promote the redistribution of nutrients throughout the tillage depth, leading to intermittent
502 releases of physically protected organic matter (Carbonetto et al. 2014). This might explain the high relative abundance
503 of *Proteobacteria* under CT compared to RT and NT, as *Proteobacteria* are rapidly growing organisms and commonly
504 associated with copiotrophic features. Contrary to what was found in this study, Ramirez-Villanueva et al. (2015)
505 reported that the relative abundance of *Actinobacteria* was higher in soil with conventional practices in relation to
506 conservation tillage practices, whereas we found that after 290 days a higher relative abundance of this phylum was
507 under RT and NT. Fairly, the influence can be context-dependent, and in the study of assessing the successional
508 patterns of decomposing wheat straw in a microcosm experiment discovered, that some taxa belonging to
509 *Actinobacteria* increased in later stages of decomposition (Bastian et al. 2009). Moreover, it is important to highlight
510 that the high C/N ratio present in some *Endocalcaric Epigleyic Cambisol* soils (Šarūnaitė et al. 2024) can promote the
511 proliferation of specific microbial groups, particularly *Actinobacteria* which are specialized in degrading more
512 recalcitrant organic materials (Bhatti et al. 2017). *Acidobacteria*, which had significantly lower relative abundance in
513 the initial wheat straw and across all tillage treatments after 145 days of decomposition, exhibited a notable increase
514 in relative abundance after 290 days of decomposition under RT. Interestingly, at lower taxonomic resolution the genus
515 *Flavobacterium*, associated with lignocellulose degradation (Jiménez et al. 2014), was rather influenced by temporal
516 changes than by the tillage factor. The bacterial genus *Pantoea*, reported to possess plenty of genes encoding potential
517 ligninolytic enzymes (Chukwuma et al. 2021; Ma et al. 2016), consequently showed a significant correlation with
518 lignin release from decomposing wheat straws.

519 Although mechanical disruptions usually damage the hyphal networks of fungi, some major classes of
520 *Basidiomycota* and *Ascomycota*, such as *Sordariomycetes* and *Leotiomyces* exhibited a greater relative abundance
521 under CT conditions. *Basidiomycota* usually consisting of saprophytic members is well known to break down more
522 complex and recalcitrant compounds, including lignin. At lower taxonomic resolution we found two genera including
523 *Tubaria* and *Agrocybe*, both belonging to *Agaricomycetes*, positively responded to RT, with variability among samples.
524 It was reported that the secretion of hydrogen peroxide is crucial in the breakdown of lignocellulose by *Agaricomycetes*
525 (Ruiz-Dueñas et al. 2021). Consequently, this supports more efficient lignin release from decomposing wheat straw
526 under RT. Interestingly, the genus *Helgardiomycetes* which was recently introduced while redefining cereal pathogen

527 genera (Crous et al. 2021), showed a significant correlation with both C and lignin release from wheat straw. This is
528 most likely due to its ability to produce a wide range of enzymes, including those that degrade lignin. Another fungal
529 genus *Sistotrema* was exclusively highly abundant only in NT after 145 and 290 days of decomposition. These white-
530 rot fungi are documented to possess an abundant number of gene copies for catalase and laccase, making this fungal
531 genus essential in lignocellulose matrix degradation (Bai et al. 2023). Moreover, consistent with previous studies, it is
532 posited that the native microbiome of the initial wheat straw plays a crucial role in the subsequent dynamics of
533 associated microbial communities (Zhong et al. 2020). Our findings provide novel insights into the wheat straw
534 decomposition process and associated microbial community composition in response to different tillage practices,
535 with implications for nutrient cycling and soil fertility. However, the study did not investigate microbial communities
536 at a taxonomic resolution finer than the genus level nor assess functional gene expression related to lignocellulose
537 degradation in decomposing wheat straw. Thus, future research should incorporate whole-genome shotgun sequencing
538 and functional analyses, such as metatranscriptomics or metaproteomics, alongside more frequent temporal sampling,
539 to offer deeper insights into the mechanisms driving microbial succession and community function.

540 **Conclusions**

541 Our study elucidates the influence of three distinct tillage practices on wheat straw decomposition and associated
542 microbial community response, with observations made after 145 days (non-growing season) and 290 days (growing
543 season), respectively. The findings demonstrate that tillage practices significantly affect temporal changes in wheat
544 straw decomposition-related variables, including decomposition rate and nutrient release dynamics. As expected,
545 increased contact between straw and soil under conventional tillage and reduced tillage significantly enhanced the
546 decomposition rate and the release of straw components, compared to surface decomposition under no-tillage.
547 Seasonal changes also played an essential role in microbial activity, thereby impacting the decomposition of wheat
548 straw. We discovered that tillage practices did not significantly alter the alpha diversity of bacterial and fungal
549 communities associated with wheat straw decomposition. However, beta diversity analysis revealed distinct microbial
550 community composition under different tillage practices. Changes in the chemical composition of decomposing wheat
551 straw, driven by different tillage practices, facilitated the proliferation of microorganisms with distinct lifestyles.
552 Conservation tillage practices, including reduced tillage and no-tillage, tended to promote microorganisms that thrive
553 in resource-limited environments. These findings address key knowledge gaps regarding the role of tillage practices

554 in sustainable residue management to enhance microbially-mediated decomposition, ultimately supporting nutrient
555 cycling and soil fertility in temperate agricultural systems.

556 **Supplementary information**

557 Figure S1. Rarefaction curves for all 28 samples produced by the rarecurve() function from the package vegan. Figure
558 S2. Rarefaction curves for all 28 samples produced by the rarecurve() function from the package vegan. Table S1.
559 Alpha-diversity of decomposition-associated bacterial communities, represented as Observed ASVs, Shannon
560 diversity and Pielou's. Table S2. Post-hoc pairwise PERMANOVA analysis (decomposition-associated bacterial
561 communities). Table S3. Alpha-diversity of decomposition-associated bacterial communities, represented as
562 Observed ASVs, Shannon diversity and Pielou's. Table S4. Post-hoc pairwise PERMANOVA analysis
563 (decomposition-associated fungal communities).

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568 **Contributions**

569 Conceptualization: Arman Shamshitov, and Skaidrė Supronienė; Methodology: Arman Shamshitov, Gražina
570 Kadžienė, Francesco Pini and Skaidrė Supronienė; Formal analysis and investigation: Arman Shamshitov, and
571 Francesco Pini; Writing - original draft preparation: Arman Shamshitov, and Francesco Pini; Writing - review and
572 editing: Arman Shamshitov; Supervision: Francesco Pini and Skaidrė Supronienė. All authors have read and approved
573 the final manuscript.

574 **Ethics declarations**

575 **Conflict of interest.** The authors declare no competing interests.

576 **Data availability**

577 Raw amplicon sequences can be found at the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under the PRJNA1175890.

578 **References**

- 579 Abarenkov K, Zirk A, Piirmann T, Pöhönen R, Ivanov F, Nilsson RH, Kõljalg U (2023) UNITE general FASTA
580 release for Fungi. UNITE Community. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15156/BIO/2938067>
- 581 Adhikari AD, Shrestha P, Ghimire R, Liu Z, Pollock DA, Acharya P, Aryal DR (2024) Cover crop residue quality
582 regulates litter decomposition dynamics and soil carbon mineralization kinetics in semi-arid cropping systems.
583 *Appl Soil Ecol* 193:105160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2023.105160>
- 584 Ankom Technology (2017) Acid Detergent Fiber in Feeds Filter Bag Technique (for A200 and A200I) ADF Method
585 Method 5. In: Ankom Technology. [https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-](https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-files/Method_5_ADF_A200.pdf?srltid=AfmBOop3vChDVtOo09ai8OzkzyzPCtK0syugiqpDIG-SwhNOyaj_xS0Gl)
586 [files/Method_5_ADF_A200.pdf?srltid=AfmBOop3vChDVtOo09ai8OzkzyzPCtK0syugiqpDIG-](https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-files/Method_5_ADF_A200.pdf?srltid=AfmBOop3vChDVtOo09ai8OzkzyzPCtK0syugiqpDIG-SwhNOyaj_xS0Gl)
587 [SwhNOyaj_xS0Gl](https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-files/Method_5_ADF_A200.pdf?srltid=AfmBOop3vChDVtOo09ai8OzkzyzPCtK0syugiqpDIG-SwhNOyaj_xS0Gl). Accessed 5 Jan 2024
- 588 Ankom Technology (2020) Determining acid detergent lignin in beakers. Method 8 Lignin in beakers. In: Ankom
589 Technology. [https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-](https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-files/Method_8_Lignin_in_beakers_120922.pdf)
590 [files/Method_8_Lignin_in_beakers_120922.pdf](https://www.ankom.com/sites/default/files/document-files/Method_8_Lignin_in_beakers_120922.pdf). Accessed 5 Jan 2024
- 591 Aylward FO, McDonald BR, Adams SM, Valenzuela A, Schmidt RA, Goodwin LA, Woyke T, Currie CR, Suen G,
592 Poulsen M (2013) Comparison of 26 Sphingomonad Genomes Reveals Diverse Environmental Adaptations
593 and Biodegradative Capabilities. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 79:3724–3733. [https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00518-](https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00518-13)
594 [13](https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00518-13)
- 595 Bai Y, Zhou Y, Chen X, An Z, Zhang X, Du J, Chang SX (2023) Tree species composition alters the decomposition
596 of mixed litter and the associated microbial community composition and function in subtropical plantations in
597 China. *For Ecol Manage* 529:120743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2022.120743>
- 598 Ball BC (2013) Soil structure and greenhouse gas emissions: a synthesis of 20 years of experimentation. *Eur J Soil*
599 *Sci* 64:357–373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12013>
- 600 Bastian F, Bouziri L, Nicolardot B, Ranjard L (2009) Impact of wheat straw decomposition on successional patterns
601 of soil microbial community structure. *Soil Biol Biochem* 41:262–275.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2008.10.024>
- 603 Benocci T, Aguilar-Pontes MV, Zhou M, Seiboth B, de Vries RP (2017) Regulators of plant biomass degradation in
604 ascomycetous fungi. *Biotechnol Biofuels* 10:152. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-017-0841-x>
- 605 Beyaert R, Paul Voroney R (2011) Estimation of decay constants for crop residues measured over 15 years in
606 conventional and reduced tillage systems in a coarse-textured soil in southern Ontario. *Can J Soil Sci* 91:985–
607 995. <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjss2010-055>
- 608 Bhatti AA, Haq S, Bhat RA (2017) Actinomycetes benefaction role in soil and plant health. *Microb Pathog* 111:458–
609 467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2017.09.036>
- 610 Bisen N, Rahangdale CP (2017) Crop residues management option for sustainable soil health in rice-wheat system:
611 A review. *Int J Chem Stud* 5:1038–1042
- 612 Bradford MA, Berg B, Maynard DS, Wieder WR, Wood SA (2016) Understanding the dominant controls on litter
613 decomposition. *J Ecol* 104:229–238. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12507>
- 614 Cabrera ML, Kissel DE, Vigil MF (2005) Nitrogen Mineralization from Organic Residues. *J Environ Qual* 34:75–
615 79. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2005.0075>
- 616 Cai L, Guo Z, Zhang J, Gai Z, Liu J, Meng Q, Liu X (2021) No tillage and residue mulching method on bacterial
617 community diversity regulation in a black soil region of Northeastern China. *PLoS One* 16:e0256970.
618 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256970>

- 619 Callahan BJ, McMurdie PJ, Rosen MJ, Han AW, Johnson AJA, Holmes SP (2016) DADA2: High-resolution sample
620 inference from Illumina amplicon data. *Nat Methods* 13:581–583. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3869>
- 621 Carbonetto B, Rascovan N, Álvarez R, Mentaberry A, Vázquez MP (2014) Structure, Composition and
622 Metagenomic Profile of Soil Microbiomes Associated to Agricultural Land Use and Tillage Systems in
623 Argentine Pampas. *PLoS One* 9:e99949. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0099949>
- 624 Carmona CP, Guerrero I, Peco B, Morales MB, Oñate JJ, Pärt T, Tschardtke T, Liira J, Aavik T, Emmerson M,
625 Berendse F, Ceryngier P, Bretagnolle V, Weisser WW, Bengtsson J (2020) Agriculture intensification reduces
626 plant taxonomic and functional diversity across European arable systems. *Funct Ecol* 34:1448–1460.
627 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.13608>
- 628 Chatterjee A, Acharya U (2020) Controls of carbon and nitrogen releases during crops' residue decomposition in the
629 Red River Valley, USA. *Arch Agron Soil Sci* 66:614–624. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03650340.2019.1630732>
- 630 Chen C, Zhang J, Lu M, Qin C, Chen Y, Yang L, Huang Q, Wang J, Shen Z, Shen Q (2016) Microbial communities
631 of an arable soil treated for 8 years with organic and inorganic fertilizers. *Biol Fertil Soils* 52:455–467.
632 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-016-1089-5>
- 633 Chigineva NI, Aleksandrova AV, Tiunov AV (2009) The addition of labile carbon alters litter fungal communities
634 and decreases litter decomposition rates. *Appl Soil Ecol* 42:264–270.
635 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2009.05.001>
- 636 Chukwuma OB, Rafatullah M, Tajarudin HA, Ismail N (2021) A Review on Bacterial Contribution to Lignocellulose
637 Breakdown into Useful Bio-Products. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 18:6001.
638 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18116001>
- 639 Chung H, Park M, Madhaiyan M, Seshadri S, Song J, Cho H, Sa T (2005) Isolation and characterization of
640 phosphate solubilizing bacteria from the rhizosphere of crop plants of Korea. *Soil Biol Biochem* 37:1970–
641 1974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2005.02.025>
- 642 Cloutier M, Alcaide T, Duiker S, Bruns MA (2023) Tillage intensity and plant rhizosphere selection shape bacterial-
643 archaeal assemblage diversity and nitrogen cycling genes. *Soil Till Res* 225:105525.
644 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2022.105525>
- 645 Connell JH (1978) Diversity in Tropical Rain Forests and Coral Reefs. *Science* (1979) 199:1302–1310.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.199.4335.1302>
- 647 Crous PW, Braun U, McDonald BA, Lennox CL, Edwards J, Mann RC, Zaveri A, Linde CC, Dyer PS, Groenewald
648 JZ (2021) Redefining genera of cereal pathogens: *Oculimacula*, *Rhynchosporium* and *Spermospora*. *Fungal*
649 *Syst Evol* 7:67–98. <https://doi.org/10.3114/fuse.2021.07.04>
- 650 Curtin D, Francis GS, McCallum FM (2008) Decomposition rate of cereal straw as affected by soil placement. *Soil*
651 *Res* 46:152. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR07085>
- 652 Degruene F, Theodorakopoulos N, Dufrêne M, Colinet G, Bodson B, Hiel M-P, Taminiau B, Nezer C, Daube G,
653 Vandenberg M (2016) No favorable effect of reduced tillage on microbial community diversity in a silty loam
654 soil (Belgium). *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 224:12–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.03.017>
- 655 Di Lonardo DP, Pinzari F, Lunghini D, Maggi O, Granito VM, Persiani AM (2013) Metabolic profiling reveals a
656 functional succession of active fungi during the decay of Mediterranean plant litter. *Soil Biol Biochem*
657 60:210–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.02.001>
- 658 Dong W, Liu E, Yan C, Tian J, Zhang H, Zhang Y (2017) Impact of no tillage vs. conventional tillage on the soil
659 bacterial community structure in a winter wheat cropping succession in northern China. *Eur J Soil Biol* 80:35–
660 42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2017.03.001>

661 Doyeni MO, Suproniene S, Versulienė A, Meskauskienė L, Kadziene G (2024) Influence of the Long-Term
662 Application of Management Practices (Tillage, Cover Crop and Glyphosate) on Greenhouse Gas Emissions
663 and Soil Physical Properties. *Sustainability* 16:2859. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16072859>

664 Erickson AE (2015) Tillage Effects on Soil Aeration. In: *Predicting Tillage Effects on Soil Physical Properties and*
665 *Processes*. pp 91–104

666 FAO (2016) *Conservation Agriculture*. FAO

667 Fierer N, Bradford MA, Jackson RB (2007) Toward an ecological classification of soil bacteria. *Ecology* 88:1354–
668 1364. <https://doi.org/10.1890/05-1839>

669 Fierer N, Lauber CL, Ramirez KS, Zaneveld J, Bradford MA, Knight R (2012) Comparative metagenomic,
670 phylogenetic and physiological analyses of soil microbial communities across nitrogen gradients. *ISME J*
671 6:1007–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2011.159>

672 Friberg H, Persson P, Jensen DF, Bergkvist G (2019) Preceding crop and tillage system affect winter survival of
673 wheat and the fungal communities on young wheat roots and in soil. *FEMS Microbiol Lett* 366.
674 <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fnz189>

675 García-Ruiz R, Carranza-Gallego G, Aguilera E, González De Molina M, Guzmán GI (2019) C and N
676 mineralisation of straw of traditional and modern wheat varieties in soils of contrasting fertility. *Nutr Cycl*
677 *Agroecosyst* 113:167–179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-019-09973-4>

678 Gomez RP, Aulicino MB, Mónaco CI, Kripelz N, Cordo CA (2015) Impact of different cropping conditions and
679 tillage practices on the soil fungal abundance of a Phaeozem luvico. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*
680 13:e1102. <https://doi.org/10.5424/sjar/2015132-6556>

681 Grime JP (1973) Competitive Exclusion in Herbaceous Vegetation. *Nature* 242:344–347.
682 <https://doi.org/10.1038/242344a0>

683 Guan Y, Wu M, Che S, Yuan S, Yang X, Li S, Tian P, Wu L, Yang M, Wu Z (2023) Effects of Continuous Straw
684 Returning on Soil Functional Microorganisms and Microbial Communities. *Journal of Microbiology* 61:49–
685 62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12275-022-00004-6>

686 Haas E, Carozzi M, Massad RS, Butterbach-Bahl K, Scheer C (2022) Long term impact of residue management on
687 soil organic carbon stocks and nitrous oxide emissions from European croplands. *Sci Total Environ*
688 836:154932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154932>

689 Habets S, de Wild PJ, Huijgen WJJ, van Eck ERH (2013) The influence of thermochemical treatments on the
690 lignocellulosic structure of wheat straw as studied by natural abundance ¹³C NMR. *Bioresour Technol*
691 146:585–590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.07.104>

692 Hidalgo C, Merino A, Osorio-Hernández V, Etchevers JD, Figueroa B, Limon-Ortega A, Aguirre E (2019) Physical
693 and chemical processes determining soil organic matter dynamics in a managed vertisol in a tropical dryland
694 area. *Soil Till Res* 194:104348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.104348>

695 Ho A, Lonardo DP Di, Bodelier PLE (2017) Revisiting life strategy concepts in environmental microbial ecology.
696 *FEMS Microbiol Ecol* 93:fix006. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fix006>

697 Ibáñez A, Sombrero A, Santiago-Pajón A, Santiago-Calvo Y, Asensio-S.-Manzanera MC (2024) Effect of long-term
698 conservation tillage management on microbial diversity under Mediterranean rainfed conditions. *Soil Till Res*
699 236:105923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2023.105923>

700 Islam MdR, Singh B, Dijkstra FA (2022) Stabilisation of soil organic matter: interactions between clay and
701 microbes. *Biogeochemistry* 160:145–158. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-022-00956-2>

- 702 ISO 11261:1995 (1995) Soil quality-Determination of total nitrogen-Modified Kjeldahl method
- 703 ISO 14235:1998 (1998) Soil quality-Determination of organic carbon by sulfochromic oxidation
- 704 IUSS Working Group WRB (2022) IUSS Working Group WRB. 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources.
705 International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition
- 706 Jensen G, Krogstad K, Rezanezhad F, Hug LA (2022) Microbial Community Compositional Stability in Agricultural
707 Soils During Freeze-Thaw and Fertilizer Stress. *Front Environ Sci* 10.
708 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.908568>
- 709 Jiménez DJ, Korenblum E, van Elsas JD (2014) Novel multispecies microbial consortia involved in lignocellulose
710 and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural bioconversion. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 98:2789–2803.
711 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-013-5253-7>
- 712 Jiménez-Bueno NG, Valenzuela-Encinas C, Marsch R, Ortiz-Gutiérrez D, Verhulst N, Govaerts B, Dendooven L,
713 Navarro-Noya YE (2016) Bacterial indicator taxa in soils under different long-term agricultural management.
714 *J Appl Microbiol* 120:921–933. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.13072>
- 715 Johnson JM-F, Barbour NW, Weyers SL (2007) Chemical Composition of Crop Biomass Impacts Its Decomposition.
716 *Soil Sci Soc Am J* 71:155–162. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2005.0419>
- 717 Kan Z-R, Ma S-T, Liu Q-Y, Liu B-Y, Virk AL, Qi J-Y, Zhao X, Lal R, Zhang H-L (2020) Carbon sequestration and
718 mineralization in soil aggregates under long-term conservation tillage in the North China Plain. *Catena (Amst)*
719 188:104428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2019.104428>
- 720 Kaurin A, Mihelič R, Kastelec D, Schloter M, Suhadolc M, Grčman H (2015) Consequences of minimum soil tillage
721 on abiotic soil properties and composition of microbial communities in a shallow Cambisol originated from
722 fluvioglacial deposits. *Biol Fertil Soils* 51:923–933. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-015-1037-9>
- 723 Kerdraon L, Balesdent M-H, Barret M, Laval V, Suffert F (2019) Crop Residues in Wheat-Oilseed Rape Rotation
724 System: a Pivotal, Shifting Platform for Microbial Meetings. *Microb Ecol* 77:931–945.
725 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-019-01340-8>
- 726 Kok DD, Scherer L, de Vries W, Trimbos K, van Bodegom PM (2022) Relationships of priming effects with organic
727 amendment composition and soil microbial properties. *Geoderma* 422:115951.
728 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.115951>
- 729 Koskinen R, Ali-Vehmas T, Kampfer P, Laurikkala M, Tsitko I, Kostyal E, Atroshi F, Salkinoja-Salonen M (2000)
730 Characterization of Sphingomonas isolates from Finnish and Swedish drinking water distribution systems. *J*
731 *Appl Microbiol* 89:687–696. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2672.2000.01167.x>
- 732 Kraut-Cohen J, Zolti A, Shaltiel-Harpaz L, Argaman E, Rabinovich R, Green SJ, Minz D (2020) Effects of tillage
733 practices on soil microbiome and agricultural parameters. *Sci Total Environ* 705:135791.
734 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135791>
- 735 Leff JW, Jones SE, Prober SM, Barberán A, Borer ET, Firm JL, Harpole WS, Hobbie SE, Hofmockel KS, Knops
736 JMH, McCulley RL, La Pierre K, Risch AC, Seabloom EW, Schütz M, Steenbock C, Stevens CJ, Fierer N
737 (2015) Consistent responses of soil microbial communities to elevated nutrient inputs in grasslands across the
738 globe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 112:10967–10972.
739 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1508382112>
- 740 Legrand F, Picot A, Cobo-Díaz JF, Carof M, Chen W, Le Floch G (2018) Effect of tillage and static abiotic soil
741 properties on microbial diversity. *Appl Soil Ecol* 132:135–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2018.08.016>

742 Li M, He P, Guo X-L, Zhang X, Li L-J (2021a) Fifteen-year no tillage of a Mollisol with residue retention indirectly
743 affects topsoil bacterial community by altering soil properties. *Soil Till Res* 205:104804.
744 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2020.104804>

745 Li N, Lei W, Long J, Han X (2021b) Restoration of Chemical Structure of Soil Organic Matter Under Different
746 Agricultural Practices from a Severely Degraded Mollisol. *J Soil Sci Plant Nutr* 21:3132–3145.
747 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42729-021-00594-x>

748 Li XS, Wu N, Liu L, Feng YP, Xu X, Han HF, Ning TY, Li ZJ (2015) Effects of different straw recycling and tillage
749 methods on soil respiration and microbial activity. *Chin J Appl Ecol* 26:1765–1771

750 Lynch MJ, Mulvaney MJ, Hodges SC, Thompson TL, Thomason WE (2016) Decomposition, nitrogen and carbon
751 mineralization from food and cover crop residues in the central plateau of Haiti. *Springerplus* 5:973.
752 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-2651-1>

753 Ma J, Zhang K, Liao H, Hector SB, Shi X, Li J, Liu B, Xu T, Tong C, Liu X, Zhu Y (2016) Genomic and secretomic
754 insight into lignocellulolytic system of an endophytic bacterium *Pantoea ananatis* Sd-1. *Biotechnol Biofuels*
755 9:25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-016-0439-8>

756 Martin M (2011) Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads. *EMBnet J* 17:10.
757 <https://doi.org/10.14806/ej.17.1.200>

758 Mathew RP, Feng Y, Githinji L, Ankumah R, Balkcom KS (2012) Impact of No-Tillage and Conventional Tillage
759 Systems on Soil Microbial Communities. *Appl Environ Soil Sci* 2012:1–10.
760 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/548620>

761 Melillo JM, Aber JD, Muratore JF (1982) Nitrogen and Lignin Control of Hardwood Leaf Litter Decomposition
762 Dynamics. *Ecology* 63:621–626. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1936780>

763 Navarro-Noya YE, Chávez-Romero Y, Hereira-Pacheco S, de León Lorenzana AS, Govaerts B, Verhulst N,
764 Dendooven L (2022) Bacterial Communities in the Rhizosphere at Different Growth Stages of Maize
765 Cultivated in Soil Under Conventional and Conservation Agricultural Practices. *Microbiol Spectr* 10.
766 <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.01834-21>

767 Nivelte E, Verzeaux J, Habbib H, Kuzyakov Y, Decocq G, Roger D, Lacoux J, Duclercq J, Spicher F, Nava-Saucedo
768 J-E, Catterou M, Dubois F, Tetu T (2016) Functional response of soil microbial communities to tillage, cover
769 crops and nitrogen fertilization. *Appl Soil Ecol* 108:147–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2016.08.004>

770 Oksanen J, Legendre P, O’Hara B, Stevens MHH, Oksanen MJ, Suggests M (2020) *Vegan: Community Ecology*
771 *Package*. R package version 2.5-7. *Community ecology package* 10

772 Olson JS (1963) Energy Storage and the Balance of Producers and Decomposers in Ecological Systems. *Ecology*
773 44:322–331. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1932179>

774 Orrù L, Canfora L, Trincherà A, Migliore M, Pennelli B, Marcucci A, Farina R, Pinzari F (2021) How Tillage and
775 Crop Rotation Change the Distribution Pattern of Fungi. *Front Microbiol* 12:634325.
776 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.634325>

777 Pascault N, Cécillon L, Mathieu O, Hénault C, Sarr A, Lévêque J, Farcy P, Ranjard L, Maron P-A (2010a) In Situ
778 Dynamics of Microbial Communities during Decomposition of Wheat, Rape, and Alfalfa Residues. *Microb*
779 *Ecol* 60:816–828. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-010-9705-7>

780 Pascault N, Nicolardot B, Bastian F, Thiébeau P, Ranjard L, Maron P-A (2010b) In Situ Dynamics and Spatial
781 Heterogeneity of Soil Bacterial Communities Under Different Crop Residue Management. *Microb Ecol*
782 60:291–303. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-010-9648-z>

- 783 Pepe-Ranney C, Campbell AN, Koechli CN, Berthrong S, Buckley DH (2016) Unearthing the Ecology of Soil
784 Microorganisms Using a High Resolution DNA-SIP Approach to Explore Cellulose and Xylose Metabolism in
785 Soil. *Front Microbiol* 7:703. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.00703>
- 786 Pittarello M, Dal Ferro N, Chiarini F, Morari F, Carletti P (2021) Influence of Tillage and Crop Rotations in Organic
787 and Conventional Farming Systems on Soil Organic Matter, Bulk Density and Enzymatic Activities in a Short-
788 Term Field Experiment. *Agronomy* 11:724. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11040724>
- 789 Poudel P, Parajuli B, Park D, Ye R (2023) Cover Crop Residues Decomposition and Nutrient Releases in a Sandy
790 Ultisols of U.S. Coastal Plain: Impacts of Termination Timing. *Commun Soil Sci Plant Anal* 54:2394–2411.
791 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103624.2023.2223612>
- 792 Pu C, Kan Z, Liu P, Ma S, Qi J, Zhao X, Zhang H (2019) Residue management induced changes in soil organic
793 carbon and total nitrogen under different tillage practices in the North China Plain. *J Integr Agric* 18:1337–
794 1347. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119\(18\)62079-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119(18)62079-9)
- 795 R Core Team (2023) R Core Team 2023 R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R foundation for
796 statistical computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>. R Foundation for Statistical Computing
- 797 Ramirez-Villanueva DA, Bello-López JM, Navarro-Noya YE, Luna-Guido M, Verhulst N, Govaerts B, Dendooven
798 L (2015) Bacterial community structure in maize residue amended soil with contrasting management practices.
799 *Appl Soil Ecol* 90:49–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2015.01.010>
- 800 Reichel R, Wei J, Islam MS, Schmid C, Wissel H, Schröder P, Schlöter M, Brüggemann N (2018) Potential of Wheat
801 Straw, Spruce Sawdust, and Lignin as High Organic Carbon Soil Amendments to Improve Agricultural
802 Nitrogen Retention Capacity: An Incubation Study. *Front Plant Sci* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.00900>
- 803 Rezig FAM, Elhadi EA, Abdalla MR (2014) Decomposition and nutrient release pattern of wheat (*Triticum*
804 *aestivum*) residues under different treatments in desert field conditions of Sudan. *Int J Recycl Org Waste Agric*
805 3:10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40093-014-0069-8>
- 806 Ruiz-Dueñas FJ, Barrasa JM, Sánchez-García M, Camarero S, Miyauchi S, Serrano A, Linde D, Babiker R, Drula E,
807 Ayuso-Fernández I, Pacheco R, Padilla G, Ferreira P, Barriuso J, Kellner H, Castanera R, Alfaro M, Ramírez
808 L, Pisabarro AG, Riley R, Kuo A, Andreopoulos W, LaButti K, Pangilinan J, Tritt A, Lipzen A, He G, Yan M,
809 Ng V, Grigoriev I V, Cullen D, Martin F, Rosso M-N, Henrissat B, Hibbett D, Martínez AT (2021) Genomic
810 Analysis Enlightens Agaricales Lifestyle Evolution and Increasing Peroxidase Diversity. *Mol Biol Evol*
811 38:1428–1446. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msaa301>
- 812 Šarūnaitė L, Arlauskienė A, Jablonskytė-Raščė D (2024) Effect of plant edges strips on the conservation soil
813 properties in modern farming field. *PLoS One* 19:e0299104. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0299104>
- 814 Schmidt R, Gravuer K, Bossange A V., Mitchell J, Scow K (2018) Long-term use of cover crops and no-till shift soil
815 microbial community life strategies in agricultural soil. *PLoS One* 13:e0192953.
816 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192953>
- 817 Senechkin I V., Speksnijder AGCL, Semenov AM, van Bruggen AHC, van Overbeek LS (2010) Isolation and Partial
818 Characterization of Bacterial Strains on Low Organic Carbon Medium from Soils Fertilized with Different
819 Organic Amendments. *Microb Ecol* 60:829–839. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-010-9670-1>
- 820 Shamshitov A, Decorosi F, Viti C, Fornasier F, Kadžienė G, Supronienė S (2022) Characterisation of Cellulolytic
821 Bacteria Isolated from Agricultural Soil in Central Lithuania. *Sustainability* 15:598.
822 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010598>
- 823 Shamshitov A, Kadžienė G, Supronienė S (2024) The Role of Soil Microbial Consortia in Sustainable Cereal Crop
824 Residue Management. *Plants* 13:766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants13060766>

- 825 Simmons BL, Coleman DC (2008) Microbial community response to transition from conventional to conservation
826 tillage in cotton fields. *Appl Soil Ecol* 40:518–528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2008.08.003>
- 827 Singh G, Dhakal M, Yang L, Kaur G, Williard KWJ, Schoonover JE, Sadeghpour A (2020) Decomposition and
828 nitrogen release of cover crops in reduced- and no-tillage systems. *Agron J* 112:3605–3618.
829 <https://doi.org/10.1002/agj2.20268>
- 830 Smith CR, Blair PL, Boyd C, Cody B, Hazel A, Hedrick A, Kathuria H, Khurana P, Kramer B, Muterspaw K, Peck
831 C, Sells E, Skinner J, Tegeler C, Wolfe Z (2016) Microbial community responses to soil tillage and crop
832 rotation in a corn/soybean agroecosystem. *Ecol Evol* 6:8075–8084. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.2553>
- 833 Su Y, Yu M, Xi H, Lv J, Ma Z, Kou C, Shen A (2020) Soil microbial community shifts with long-term of different
834 straw return in wheat-corn rotation system. *Sci Rep* 10:6360. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-63409-6>
- 835 Sun R, Li W, Dong W, Tian Y, Hu C, Liu B (2018) Tillage Changes Vertical Distribution of Soil Bacterial and
836 Fungal Communities. *Front Microbiol* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00699>
- 837 Takahashi S, Tomita J, Nishioka K, Hisada T, Nishijima M (2014) Development of a Prokaryotic Universal Primer
838 for Simultaneous Analysis of Bacteria and Archaea Using Next-Generation Sequencing. *PLoS One* 9:e105592.
839 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0105592>
- 840 Toju H, Tanabe AS, Yamamoto S, Sato H (2012) High-Coverage ITS Primers for the DNA-Based Identification of
841 Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes in Environmental Samples. *PLoS One* 7:e40863.
842 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0040863>
- 843 Toleikiene M, Arlauskiene A, Fliessbach A, Iqbal R, Sarunaite L, Kadziuliene Z (2020) The decomposition of
844 standardised organic materials in loam and clay loam arable soils during a non-vegetation period. *Soil Water*
845 *Res* 15:181–190. <https://doi.org/10.17221/31/2019-SWR>
- 846 Turmel M-S, Speratti A, Baudron F, Verhulst N, Govaerts B (2015) Crop residue management and soil health: A
847 systems analysis. *Agric Syst* 134:6–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2014.05.009>
- 848 Tyler HL (2019) Bacterial community composition under long-term reduced tillage and no till management. *J Appl*
849 *Microbiol* 126:1797–1807. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14267>
- 850 Urakawa R, Shibata H, Kuroiwa M, Inagaki Y, Tateno R, Hishi T, Fukuzawa K, Hirai K, Toda H, Oyanagi N, Nakata
851 M, Nakanishi A, Fukushima K, Enoki T, Suwa Y (2014) Effects of freeze–thaw cycles resulting from winter
852 climate change on soil nitrogen cycling in ten temperate forest ecosystems throughout the Japanese
853 archipelago. *Soil Biol Biochem* 74:82–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2014.02.022>
- 854 Wang H, Guo Z, Shi Y, Zhang Y, Yu Z (2015) Impact of tillage practices on nitrogen accumulation and translocation
855 in wheat and soil nitrate-nitrogen leaching in drylands. *Soil Tillage Res* 153:20–27.
856 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2015.03.006>
- 857 Wang H, Wang L, Zhang Y, Hu Y, Wu J, Fu X, Le Y (2017a) The variability and causes of organic carbon retention
858 ability of different agricultural straw types returned to soil. *Environ Technol* 38:538–548.
859 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2016.1201545>
- 860 Wang Z, Li T, Wen X, Liu Y, Han J, Liao Y, DeBruyn JM (2017b) Fungal Communities in Rhizosphere Soil under
861 Conservation Tillage Shift in Response to Plant Growth. *Front Microbiol* 8.
862 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01301>
- 863 Wang Z, Liu L, Chen Q, Wen X, Liu Y, Han J, Liao Y (2017c) Conservation tillage enhances the stability of the
864 rhizosphere bacterial community responding to plant growth. *Agron Sustain Dev* 37:44.
865 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-017-0454-6>

866 White TJ, Bruns T, Lee S, Taylor J (1990) Amplification and direct sequencing of fungal ribosomal RNA genes for
867 phylogenetics. In: PCR Protocols. Elsevier, pp 315–322

868 Xu X, Pei J, Xu Y, Wang J (2020) Soil organic carbon depletion in global Mollisols regions and restoration by
869 management practices: a review. *J Soils Sediments* 20:1173–1181. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-019-02557-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-019-02557-3)
870 3

871 Yadav GS, Lal R, Meena RS, Babu S, Das A, Bhowmik SN, Datta M, Layak J, Saha P (2019) Conservation tillage
872 and nutrient management effects on productivity and soil carbon sequestration under double cropping of rice
873 in north eastern region of India. *Ecol Indic* 105:303–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.08.071>

874 Yadvinder-Singh, Bijay-Singh, Timsina J (2005) Crop Residue Management for Nutrient Cycling and Improving
875 Soil Productivity in Rice-Based Cropping Systems in the Tropics. *Adv Agron* 85:269–407.
876 [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(04\)85006-5](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(04)85006-5)

877 Yilmaz P, Parfrey LW, Yarza P, Gerken J, Pruesse E, Quast C, Schweer T, Peplies J, Ludwig W, Glöckner FO (2014)
878 The SILVA and “All-species Living Tree Project (LTP)” taxonomic frameworks. *Nucleic Acids Res* 42:D643–
879 D648. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkt1209>

880 Zhang J, Liu G, Fukasawa Y (2022a) Editorial: Fungal Genetics in Plant Biomass Conversion. *Front Microbiol* 13.
881 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.875768>

882 Zhang L, Larsson A, Moldin A, Edlund U (2022b) Comparison of lignin distribution, structure, and morphology in
883 wheat straw and wood. *Ind Crops Prod* 187:115432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.115432>

884 Zhang S, Li M, Cui X, Pan Y (2023) Effect of different straw retention techniques on soil microbial community
885 structure in wheat–maize rotation system. *Front Microbiol* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.1069458>

886 Zhang Y, Ren Y, Zhou S, Ning X, Wang X, Yang Y, Sun S, Vinay N, Bahn M, Han J, Liu Y, Xiong Y, Liao Y, Mo F
887 (2024) Spatio-temporal microbial regulation of aggregate-associated priming effects under contrasting tillage
888 practices. *Sci Total Environ* 925:171564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171564>

889 Zhao J, Ni T, Xun W, Huang X, Huang Q, Ran W, Shen B, Zhang R, Shen Q (2017) Influence of straw incorporation
890 with and without straw decomposer on soil bacterial community structure and function in a rice-wheat
891 cropping system. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 101:4761–4773. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-017-8170-3>

892 Zhong Y, Liu J, Jia X, Shangguan Z, Wang R, Yan W (2020) Microbial community assembly and metabolic function
893 during wheat straw decomposition under different nitrogen fertilization treatments. *Biol Fertil Soils* 56:697–
894 710. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-020-01438-z>

895